

THE ENGLISH EFFECT

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Annotation; In this article, the impact of the English language on the whole world is discussed. In this, several opinions were expressed, and in addition, the place in the world was widely covered.

Key words; english, effect, language, points, UK, British Council, globe, worldwide, ESL,culture.

It is obviously known that every language has its own role in the world. This is the main reason for effect of language.

It is not an indisputable fact that english is spoken at a useful level by a quarter of the world population. Combining first-hand testimony and quantitative data, this British Council report explores many facets of this global language: its characteristics and the dynamics of native and non-native use of English; the impact that English language skills have on people's lives, educational and employment prospects, and on societal stability; and the economic value of English to the UK.

Key points from The English Effect include:

English now belongs to the world, with non-native speakers far outnumbering native speakers

English gives the UK a competitive edge in areas ranging from culture and media to commerce and soft power

English boosts stability, employability and prosperity in developing and emerging economies

The UK needs to do more to respond to the global demand for English – including attracting our brightest and best young people into English teaching

The UK also needs to beware of relying too heavily on English – as foreign language skills are still essential for the UK to compete in a global economy.

Mark Robson, Director of English and Exams at the British Council, said: "The English language is perhaps the United Kingdom's greatest and yet least-recognised international asset. It is a cornerstone of our identity and it keeps us in the mind of hundreds of millions of people around the world, even when they are not talking to us."

You see why it can impact worldwide. English is what propels the global community, business, science and opportunities across societies. It allows humanity to speak in one language and understand one another better than ever before. In an interconnected world, English impacts every aspect of our lives.

In addition, English is crucial for students as it broadens their minds, develops emotional skills, improve the quality of life by providing job opportunities. Moreover, the use of English as an International language is growing with time because it is the only medium for communication in many countries.

The most vital one that it has gain globe. Speaking a common language enables you to meet new people who also speak that language, and can result in lifelong friendships that you otherwise wouldn't be able to make. As well as building relationships with people who speak English, it also gives the opportunity to learn more about other cultures.

English speaking can be improved only by practising. If you converse in English with others, it will be helpful. Watching English TV shows will also be helpful as you will read the subtitles and listen to the English terms alongside. It will help in improving your communication skills and also pronunciation.

English becomes a world language because people in other countries give a special credence to English, even though they do not speak it as a first language. Special status given to English by other countries can be in the form of using English as a second language (ESL) and English as a foreign language (EFL)

Cultural goal makes a substantial contribution:

to developing pupils' linguistic outlook, as they get acquainted with some phenomena which are not typical of their mother-tongue (e.g. tenses, articles, EL word order);

to developing pupils' communicative abilities;

to widening pupils' innovative vision of the world, as it enables them to get acquainted with the life, customs and traditions of the people whose language they study;

to developing pupils' intellect, their voluntary and involuntary memory, their imaginative abilities, logical thinking, etc.

The cultural goal is achieved within:

the critical, patient and creative attitude to oneself and others, to a new culture, event, knowledge;

the development of different character traits, outlooks, beliefs, moral-esthetic and emotional experience, different kinds of motivation and the abilities to use them to contribute successfully into the process of real and pedagogical communication;

the development of the awareness of the new activities, new people civilizations;

the development of the desire to cooperate and socialize;

the keeping cultural traditions of one's own country and understanding and respect others'; to compare different cultures, to express a personal point of view on other cultures, problems as well as to use the knowledge obtained from other subjects.

It is important to point out and note down that cultural goals are realized within the process of achieving practical objectives.

Educational and developmental goals of EL teaching and learning

The practical and cultural goals are closely connected with the educational one because FLL advances moral and aesthetic education. Teachers and methodologists pay much attention to

educational capacities in the teaching and learning process. Of great importance is the linguistic aspect - the contextual side of the material in the foreign language: texts, exercises, ostensive and audio-visual materials used in the classroom, outside school hours, and independent learning.

By way of conclusion, the goal of education is to develop individuals who adhere to definite moral principles, value knowledge and learning, can and will be able to think and find out things for themselves.

Learning, as we know, is a function of the total involvement and is the result of interactive process with students and teachers having an influence on the outcomes of such interaction. Thus, learning a FL adds to the learners' mental powers, sharpens their wits, develops their intelligence and contributes to their general outlook.

Classroom language experiences should be functional. Language use and study should fulfill purposes that are meaningful and obvious to pupils. Repeated interaction with classical literature also increases pupils' sensitivity to social, cultural dynamics and to the emotional needs of others. The teacher's role and attitude should be consistent with educational goals. "Consistency" here is one of trusting, i.e. respecting students' opinions and desires towards fairness. The "consistency" here is between having a rule and applying it in the same manner with all people including one's own.

References:

1. <https://www.google.com/search?q=the+english+effect&oq=the+english+effect&aqs=chrome..69j57.8975j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8>
2. <https://www.google.com/search?q=the+english+effect&oq=the+english+effect&aqs=chrome..69j57.8975j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-90>
3. Gardner, H. (1993). *Multiple Intelligences: The Theory in Practice*. New York, NY: BasicBooks.
4. Edwards, L. (2002). *The Creative Arts: A Process Approach for Teachers and Children*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill Prentice Hall.
5. Aggleton, Peter J., and Geoff Whitty. 1985. "Rebels Without a Cause? Socialization and Subcultural Style Among the Children of the New Middle Classes." *Sociology of Education* 58:60-72.
6. Anyon, Jean. 1981. "Social Class and School Knowledge." *Curriculum Inquiry* 11:1-42
7. Apple, Michael W. 1979. *Ideology and Curriculum*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
8. Baker, David, and David Stevenson. 1986. "Mothers' Strategies for School Achievement: Managing the Transition to High School." *Sociology of Education* 59:156-66.
9. Becker, Henry Jay, and Joyce L. Epstein. 1982. "Parent Involvement: A Survey of Teacher Practices." *Elementary School Journal* 83:85-102.
10. Berger, Eugenia H. 1983. *Beyond the Classroom: Parents as Partners in Education*. St. Louis: C.V. Mosby.
- Bernstein, Basil. 1975. *Class, Codes and Control*. Vol. 3. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul. . 1982. "Codes, Modalities and the Process of Cultural Reproduction: A Model." Pp. 304-55 in *Cultural and Economic Reproduction in Education*, edited by Michael W. Apple.
- London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Bott, Elizabeth. 1971. *Family and Social Networks*. New York: Free Press.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. 1977a. "Cultural Reproduction and Social

Reproduction." Pp. 487-511 in Power and Ideology in Education, edited by J. Karabel and A.H. Halsey. New York: Oxford University Press. . 1977b. Outline of a Theory of Practice. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. . 1981. "Men and Machines." Pp. 304-17 in Advances in Social Theory.

11. <https://blog.xabar.uz/post/maktabgacha-ta-lim-jarayonida-xorijiy-tillarni-oqitishningzamo>
12. <https://goaravetisyan.ru/uz/sekrety-obucheniya-doshkolnikov-angliiskomu-voznrastnye/>
13. <https://spbhttp.ru/uz/igra-aktivnyi-metod-obucheniya-nemeckomu-yazyku-aktivnyemetody>
14. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/xorijiy-tillarni-oqitishning-samarali-usullari-nemis-tilimisolid>
15. PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN SCHOOLS. Newjournal.org «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ» Xalqaro ilmiy jurnal. (ISSN-1281-3817)
16. IMPACTS OF ORGANIZING CLASSES USING INTERACTIVE
17. METHODS IN ENGLISH. PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS / 2022 – PART 16 /
18. TA'LIM SOHASI RIVOJLANISHIDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARNING O'RNI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences (ERUS) ISSN: 2181-3515 Sayt: <http://erus.uz/>
19. Til o'rgatishda interaktiv usullar samaradorligi masalalari. 'Tadqiqotlar' ilmiy-metodik jurnali
20. #2 soni
21. Sayt; www.tadqiqotlar.uz
22. Педагогический подход учителя к проведению урока. INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM: a collection scientific works of the International scientific conference (25th January, 2023) – Washington, USA: "CESS", 2023. Part 26 – 355
23. Involving children in English as early as kindergarten age. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION Canada International scientific-online conference
24. The significance of innovation in teaching at the University. INDIA INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC ONLINE CONFERENCE THE THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PEDAGOGY